

FORMAL WRITING STYLE IN FRENCH LANGUAGE AND ITS DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: This article presents the author's thoughts, analyzes and conclusions about formal style in French and its development. The official style has its own characteristics, and the development of this style is directly related to the formation of the literary language and the development of diplomatic, political, and social relations of the country. That is why the development of this method is considered to be of national importance.

Key words: stylistics, styles, official style, official documents, terminology, neologism, Tubon law,

Stylistics, which is considered one of the most important areas in French linguistics, deals with the identification and research of the use of language units as a means of communication in various fields and situations, the laws of speech organization, the possibilities of all tools in the language system in the speech process, and the subtleties of meaning.

One of the main works dedicated to the stylistics of the French national language, the work "Traité de stylistique française" belongs to S. Bally, a representative of the Swiss school of linguistics and a follower of Ferdinand de Saussure.[1] In the first part of this work, the linguist clearly defined the task, object, learning methods and the subject of the subject of stylistics. He also researches the stylistics of the French language in his work. The development of stylistics gave impetus to the development of formal style, which is considered an integral part of this science.

The formal writing style is an integral element of the modern literary language, and as one of the most important departments of stylistics in most languages, it has fulfilled the tasks of creating and regulating official-departmental relations.

The term "administrative style" (le style administratif) usually refers to the specific features of the language of international agreements, government documents, laws, decisions, regulations, instructions, orders, business correspondence [Мешкова 2013:302]. Departmental work style is distinguished by the wide use of special terminology of a legal, diplomatic, financial and economic nature, special phraseological devices, as well as certain neutral vocabulary and archaisms.

The formal style is characterized by clarity, objectivity of presentation, lack of imagery and emotionality, use of ready-made formulas.

It is known that the language of codes, decrees, and orders, which became the center of the emerging national literary language system, played an important role in the formation of the norms of the current French literary language. This official style language is used in state-legal documents, contracts, and departmental correspondence is conducted in this language. Elements of this language entered the literary language and directly participated in the

formation of the national literary language. The Russian linguist V. A. Kozhimiya (В. А. Кожемякина), who has conducted many scientific researches on the French official-departmental style, in his scientific works, states that the departmental work style is considered one of the oldest stylistic systems of the French language, as well as a separate study of the language of the sources of the ancient French official style, French written and literary emphasized that it had a great influence on the unification and development of syntactic norms [Кожемякина 1987:14].

The importance of studying the modern official style of work is determined not only by its contribution to the formation and formation of the literary language, but also by the importance of this style at the present time. Knowing and being able to skillfully use the language of office work is especially necessary for those who constantly work with various types of documents.

Creating documents in an official style has a long history. It is known that official documents have been kept since ancient times. Simultaneously with the appearance of writing, documentary began to develop, it served as a means of communication, exchange of ideas and mutual understanding between people. Documentary is a product of centuries, it is directly related to the history of society. Documentation also develops and improves with changes in production and work in the state apparatus.

The development of the society also brings about certain changes in the documentation system. Even in the period of the primitive community system, members of the society felt the need to record important situations in their mutual relations. Sources found in historical archeological monuments can provide sufficient information about these situations.

In France, the creation and study of documents in the official-departmental style, the formation of the official style in the form of expression, has its own historical reasons and roots, which are special and standardized. Since the 16th century, French has become the national and official language. On August 25, 1539, King François I signed the Edict of "Viller-Cotterêts" [5] and established the use of French in court proceedings and in the administration of the entire Kingdom. In these areas, dialects and Latin writings are transferred to French, the national language. At that time, official style standards began to develop. According to the "Le décret du 2 Thermidor" [6] law, collective documents in all regions of France were to be written only in French.

Subsequently, many texts were created that contributed to bringing changes and features to administrative writing that distinguish it from other types of languages.

In this context, from July 9, 1789 to September 30, 1791, the great effort of reform carried out by the National Constituent Assembly of France contributed, in particular, to the codification of administrative regulations in the development of about 2,500 laws and decrees. It should be noted that the purpose of the agents of the administration was as follows:

- rules applicable between superiors and subordinates and vice versa;
- official mailings and handling;
- principles of signing;
- and clarification of the tone used in administrative correspondence.

Law No. 75-1349 of December 31, 1975 on the Use of the French Language, Constitutional Law of June 25, 1992 and Law of August 4, 1994 (Toubon Law. No. 94-665 of August 4, 1994 the law, known as the Tubon Law [7], named after the then Minister of Culture

Jacques Tubon, aimed at protecting the heritage of the French language) the main objectives of the law are: language enrichment, the obligation to use the French language, French was to protect the language as the state language in the republic. These laws also aim to ensure that traditional French terms take precedence over English words.

The General Commission on Terminology and Neologisms published its pamphlet "Répertoire terminologique" in its official journal of September 22, 2000. This book is a revised version of the list of terms published before 1996, and includes words related to official documents written in French today.

"Le style administrative" manual, created by R. Catherine, published by Albin Michel, has been used since the middle of the 20th century until today to work with documents written in the official-departmental style of the French language and to learn this style. published 8 times (1947, 1968, 1979, 1982, 1985, 1988, 1996, 2005). In the preface of this manual, the repeated publication of this book is explained as follows: "Since the last edition, significant changes have occurred in our field of management, we decided to enrich this work with new information in the field.

Once again, various references to administrative style have been reviewed and critically revised to guide the reader as rationally as possible through the tradition of bureaucratic language." (author's translation) [Catherine 2005: 7] Our vision it is possible that the formal style of the French language is constantly changing, which indicates that there is a constant need for this style to be studied and researched.

In conclusion, it should be noted that there are many literatures, manuals and instructions in many other languages about working in an official-departmental style. In addition to providing methodological assistance to relevant employees in their work, they provide commonality and uniformity in the working papers of the departments, and allow linguists conducting research in this field to study and analyze the changes taking place in the official-departmental style

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